

PLAN OF THE ISLAMIC SITE OF CHAHAH IN THE MINAB OASIS

N

Mounded
Area

Tidal Creek

Sea
Wall

Sea
Wall

Tidal
Creek

Jetty

SCALE

100 200 300 400 metres

A. G. Williamson